

Backscattered Electrons Spectra and Angular Distributions: Simulations with EGS5

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Abstract—The purpose of the present study is to compare numerical Monte Carlo simulations of backscattering of electrons, mainly in the keV range, with available experimental data. The final goal is to assess the ability of the Monte Carlo code to predict viable results, in view of the complexity and difficulty of performing experimental measurements. A specific code for simulating electrons backscattering was developed, based on the EGS5 electron-photon transport routines. The code was parallelized very efficiently for a common memory configuration. Simulation results for the backscattering coefficient η , the energy spectrum $d\eta/dq$, and the angle dependent energy spectrum $d\eta/dqd\Omega$ were obtained. Comparing with experiments shows agreement from very good to fair, especially in regions of high q (energy) values. For low values of q there are not experimental results due to difficulties in measurements. Hence, the Monte Carlo program can provide good estimates, in the range of energies from tens of keV up to 100-200 keV.

Index Terms—Low Energy; Electron Scattering; Backscattering Coefficient; EGS5 Simulation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Backscattering of electrons is used as an investigating tool in many fields of physical sciences, like surface science, thin films, diffraction, etc. Corrections in electron probe microanalysis need knowledge of the energy distribution of the backscattered electrons. The resolution of the SEM (scanning electron microscope) is influenced by backscattering of the primary electrons and the production of secondary electrons. The phenomenon is also of interest in medical physics where accurate knowledge of deposited dose and collateral damage is important. Measuring electrons backscattering in the kilovolt range is very difficult to perform and it is prone to many experimental errors, varying with the technique employed (a good discussion on the subject is given by Niedrig [1]).

It is of interest to have tools capable of reproducing and predicting the behavior of electrons under a variety of conditions. Not only of the straightforward backscattering coefficient η (defined as the ratio of the backscattered electrons to the total number of electrons), but of more detailed quantities like energy distributions (spectra) $d\eta(E)/dE$, angular distributions $d\eta(\theta)/d\Omega$, and even the double differential $d\eta(E,\theta)/dEd\Omega$, i.e. the angle dependent energy spectra. Good (or only) candidates for such a tool are the general Monte Carlo codes, which possess many different physical models, depending on energy or other parameters,

being able to function under a variety of conditions. The codes have to be tested against actual measurements to assess their performance.

A number of works are dedicated to compare Monte Carlo codes results with the electron backscattering experiments: Seltzer and Berger [2] with ETRAN; Ferrari *et al.* [3] with FLUKA; Baró *et al.* [4] with PENELOPE; Ito *et al.* [5] with ITS 3.0.

Of particular interest is the work Ali and Rogers [6], who, with the EGSnrc [7] system conducted an analysis on a large number of experiments. The present work makes a similar investigation but differs in two important aspects. The spectra calculated by Ali and Rogers and the experimental data were arbitrarily renormalized such that, essentially, only the similarity of their shapes was verified. The aim of the present work is to compare absolute data against absolute calculations results. This will give a measure of the predictive power of the Monte Carlo code. We will focus on a smaller number of experiments but try to reproduce most of their published data. The employed system here is EGS5 [8]. A smaller number of experiments are analyzed but a) they were left out from the Ali and Rogers work and b) the analysis is more in depth.

While both EGSnrc and EGS5 are decedents of the original EGS4 [9] developed at SLAC, they followed rather different paths of evolution employing, in some places, not identical algorithms. EGSnrc (developed at NRC in Canada) still maintains the (strange) EGS4 procedure of using an old interpreter (MORTRAN): a user develops an application in a macro language, MORTRAN translates it to FORTRAN (together with many other macros of the EGS system itself) and then a compilation of the whole bundle, including parts untouched at all, is done. The procedure is repeated for every big or small change in the application making the development cycle tedious. EGS5 (developed at KEK in Japan) is a modern collection of routines written directly in FORTRAN. While, as it is distributed, one has to recompile all these routines for every change, it is quite easy to produce a library, such that a user can concentrate only on the four or five routines of his application. This is similar to the usage mode of Geant4 and makes EGS5 more of a user program, rather than a specialist's program, enlarging its attractiveness. Moreover, the distribution contains also a combinatorial geometry addition, developed by Torii and Sugita [10]. Using it, a user benefits of considerable less headaches in including some more complex geometries, not a minor problem in EGS, and, no need at all to write a HOWFAR routine, one being present in this addition. A visualization program is available

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as a separate download. Additionally, the EGS5 eliminates at all the need for a HOWNEAR routine. In view of these additional benefits it is worthwhile to test the performance of EGS5 against actual measured data.

EGS5 was used before, in simulating backscattering of electrons, by Kiriara [11] *et al.*

II. METHODS

A dedicated Monte Carlo simulation program was developed, based on the EGS5 system routines and methodology. The employed geometry is simple planar consisting of three regions: 1st region, vacuum before the sample, 2nd region, the sample foil and the 3rd region vacuum after the sample. The bombarding electron is initiated in the 1st region and also the backscattered electrons are counted there, if their momentum is oriented backwards. The transmitted electrons can be sampled in the 3rd region but are not an object of investigation in this study.

The present work uses an advanced feature of modern FORTRAN compilers, namely compilation with the *coarray* option. A program compiled with coarray will produce, at the run time, identical images (threads) running on all the available cores of a processor. They are running in parallel, one thread per core. If each core initiates its random number generator with a different seed, at the end of the run, there will be *ncores* different results of the same "Monte Carlo experiment". The method is beneficial when running on XEON processors with many cores. Furthermore, a number of quantities, especially the ones used for scoring, should be declared specifically as coarrays. This permits, at the end of the run, to be gathered and averaged reducing the variance. This is similar to a technique, used in the original EGS4 programs, of dividing the run in batches and averaging. The difference is that the total running time is *ncores* times shorter, for the same number of initial electrons.

III. RESULTS

A. The measurements of Martin *et al.*

Martin and coworkers [12]-[13] published two papers, which report the backscattering of electrons from Beryllium, EJ204 - an organic scintillator, and Silicon. They presented results for the backscattering coefficient η at five energies in 43.5 – 124 keV range, angular distributions and double differential spectra at 124 keV and 7 angles. In addition, simulations with Geant4 and Penelope were reported. The backscattering coefficient η was measured by two methods: 1) with a Silicon detector, and 2) by current integration from the walls of the scattering chamber. The results do not coincide.

Martin *et al.* reported difficulties with the Geant4 simulations, they had to reduce the maximum step length permitted for the electrons and had to adjust two undocumented parameters to fix the multiple scattering of the electrons and their ionization. Even then, Penelope gave better results.

For checking purpose, simulations with Geant4 were also done in the present work, in addition to EGS5. For this, we used the example TestEm5 found in the Geant4 collection of

examples in the folder */examples/extended/electromagnetic*. It deals with transmission, reflection and absorption of particles through or from an absorber. It calculates the backscattering coefficient η and among the others quantities, the histograms #30 and #32 are directly related with the quantities $d\eta/dE$ and $d\eta/d\Omega$. For the angle dependent spectra one can add a two dimensional histogram, but was more convenient to add 7 one-dimensional histograms in energy, one for each angle. This is so because one-dimensional histograms can be simply printed to an ascii file by a user interface command, while ROOT programming is needed to extract data from a two dimensional histogram. The cuts for both electrons and photons were put at 1 μm , giving energy cuts about 1 keV – similar to those in EGS5. All the secondaries were killed in the StackingAction routine. No particular dependence on StepMax parameter was observed. Taking notice of the problems with multiple scattering reported by Martin *et al.*, tests were done to study the influence of the physics lists (collections of physical models – peculiar to Geant4) on the results (the present paper uses experimental data digitized from the original figures):

TABLE I: GEANT4 PHYSICS LISTS USED IN SIMULATIONS OF THE BACKSCATTERING COEFFICIENTS MEASURED AT 124 KEV.

PhysicsList	Target experiment	Be 2.76%	EJ204 4.51%	Si 16.72%
emstandard_opt3		1.68%	2.71%	14.40%
empenelope		1.62%	3.01%	14.54%
emlivermore		1.68%	2.99%	14.72%
local		1.66%	2.57%	14.11%
emlowenergy		1.91%	2.88%	15.45%
emstandard_WVI		2.02%	3.15%	14.75%
standardGS		2.39%	3.44%	14.83%

In general, Geant4 gives results lower than the experimental measurements. More so, when using the *usual* physics lists like standard_opt3, Livermore or Penelope. The list emlowenergy performs surprisingly well for Silicon but it is not particularly good for the other two. The standardGS gives consistently values closer to experiment, it is not defined in the TestEm5 documentation but it is probably based on Goudsmit and Saunderson [14] theory of multiple scattering. In the following, we used emstandard_WVI, the second best choice, which is defined as standard electromagnetic physics plus Wentzel_VI multiple scattering [15]-[16]. The problems experienced by Martin *et al.* with the multiple scattering are confirmed by this choice. More information on the physics of Geant4 regarding the electrons can be found in a preprint by Sung [17].

It should be stressed that the EGS5 simulations are *out of the box*, i.e. no special parameters, no special physics, no physics list or something similar. All the bonus effects, like Rayleigh scattering, Compton broadening, fluorescence, Auger were included in the cross sections prepared with **pegs5**. It is not clear if they have any effect, with the probable exception of the electron impact ionization, because they are relevant to photons interactions, while here there is an electron problem.

In order to be sure that the backscattering is analyzed, only the first electron on the stack was considered in scoring in the

hope that this was also the primary electron (see a discussion latter).

1) The backscattering coefficient η

Fig. 1. Backscattering coefficients measured in the works [12]-[13]

Fig. 1 presents the measured and calculated backscattering coefficients relevant to the works of Martin *et al.* In Beryllium and EJ204 scintillator EGS5 simulations clearly are in favor of the Si detector results while Geant4 stays below the measurements. In Silicon, EGS5 and Geant4 agree very well and both are staying in between the Si detector and current integration results.

2) Angular distributions $d\eta(\theta)/d\Omega$

The electron beam travels towards the $-z$, at normal incidence, and meets the material slab at $z=0$. In these coordinates the backscattering angles have values $\theta < 90^\circ$.

Fig. 2 shows the angular distributions measured by Martin *et al.* with 124 keV electrons. These data come, necessarily, from the Si detector measurements. Geant4 systematically underestimates them, but in Silicon it is quite close. EGS5 presents very nice agreement in EJ204 and Silicon but overshoots at angles lower than 60° in Beryllium. It is not clear why. A look at Fig. 1 shows quite good agreement for the backscattering coefficient η at 124 keV in Beryllium. Hence, it was expected that this agreement will show up also in the angular distribution. The angular distribution should comply with the consistency check:

$$\int \frac{d\eta}{d\Omega} d\Omega = \eta \quad (1)$$

The EGS5 calculations are consistent by definition (they were also checked manually). It can be guessed that it is not the case with the experimental Beryllium data. One cannot check this assumption because the interval $0 - 20^\circ$, which will give a major contribution to the above integral, was not measured.

Fig. 2. Angular distributions of the 124 keV electrons, measured in [12].

3) The angle dependent spectra $d\eta(q, \theta)/dq d\Omega$

The angle dependent energy spectra are given as a function of the parameter q , where q is defined as the ratio E/E_{\max} . Without any additional considerations the spectra should end at $q=1$. Experimentally this is not the case. The Si detector has a resolution (σ) of 3 keV which smears the data and a signal appears also at $q > 1$. This smearing was modeled in the present EGS5 simulations.

There is need for long runs and high statistics to simulate the spectra; otherwise, the histograms will appear very jumpy. A $dq=0.01$ step was employed giving histograms of 108 points ($3 \cdot \sigma$ beyond E_{\max}). The results presented here were obtained with a Xeon with 12 cores, 4×10^6 shots per image, totalizing almost 5×10^7 total shots. The time for such a run was 8 minutes. The time for a Geant4 simulation, parallelized by their own multithreading technique, for the same statistics and same processor, was more than one hour.

Due to experimental problems, data was taken only for $q > 0.2$. In this work, a consistency condition of the type:

$$\int \frac{d\eta}{dq d\Omega} dq = \frac{d\eta}{d\Omega} \quad (2)$$

was enforced on the experimental data in the following way: 1) the EGS5 result was integrated in the regions $0 < q < 0.2$ and $0.2 < q < q_{\max}$. The ratio f of the smaller to the larger regions was calculated; 2) the experimental data was integrated from $q=0.2$ to q_{\max} and multiplied by $(1+f)$. In this way, an estimate of the missing data was added to the experimental results; 3) the final integral was compared with the experimental $d\eta/d\Omega$ and a renormalization factor was deduced. In general, the $d\eta/dq d\Omega$ was renormalized such that the condition above should be obeyed, on the grounds that $d\eta/d\Omega$ is easier to measure and hence, more accurate. The correction factor f was, in general, of the order of a couple of percent up to 10% in the more difficult cases.

Fig. 3. Angle dependent energy spectra from Silicon at θ from 20° to 70° . Normal incident electrons of 124 keV. Experimental data from [12]-[13], red lines.

Fig. 4. Angle dependent energy spectra from EJ204 at θ from 20° to 70° . Normal incident electrons of 124 keV. Experimental data from [12]-[13], red lines.

Most of the spectra are presented in Fig. 3, Fig. 4 and Fig. 5. The Beryllium spectra shows the same problem as in Fig. 2, namely they are between the EGS5 and Geant4 simulations. Reasons for this were already pointed out. In Silicon and EJ204 scintillator there is a nice agreement with EGS5. The spectra show a peak somewhere around $q=0.5$. The agreement is much better at higher q 's (energies). At lower energies the experimental spectra are too high, reflecting probably the experimental reasons why no measurements were made at all at $q < 0.2$.

Fig. 5. Angle dependent energy spectra from Beryllium at θ from 20° to 70° . Normal incident electrons of 124 keV. Experimental data from [12]-[13], red lines.

This is a complete analysis of the experiments of Martin *et al.* No data was left out.

B. The measurements of Matsukawa *et al.*

A conspicuous absence in the work of Martin *et al.* is the lack of total energy spectra $d\eta/dq$. On the other hand, the work of Matsukawa *et al.* [18] is specifically dedicated to the measurements of energy distributions. Measurements were done, at 10-30 keV, on C, Al, Cu, Au and Cu-Au alloys. Moreover, incident angles α , different from zero, were also used. The resolution was 2%.

Fig. 6 shows energy spectra obtained with 20 keV incident electrons from C and Al. For normal incident angles ($\alpha=0^\circ$) quite good agreement with the EGS5 simulations is obtained. For $\alpha \neq 0^\circ$ there are obvious problems. These disagreements are not specific to EGS5. It can be seen that EGSnr (calculated with the program available on the site of its author - D. W. O. Rogers) and Geant4 do not produce better results. EGSnr calculates the *true* energy spectrum $d\eta/dE$, hence, was multiplied by the Jacobian $|dE/dq|=20$ keV.

Fig. 6. Energy spectra from C and Al, obtained with 20 keV incident electrons at different incident angles α . The EGSnr calculation does not model the detector resolution.

Only two angle dependent energy spectra are given by Matsukawa *et al.* and only on a relative scale. They were obtained with 20 keV incident electrons.

Fig. 7. Left side: angle dependent energy spectra. Right side: total energy spectra. Experimental data from [18], red lines.

The geometry of the experiment, for these two spectra, is given by Matsukawa in angles relative to the xy plane. In the general coordinate system, the angle of incidence is $\alpha=60^\circ$

and a Si detector is placed at 80° (in the opposite side of the z-axis relative to the beam) or 0° (backscattering, on the - axis). After an arbitrary normalization of the EGS5 simulation a good qualitative agreement is obtained at $\theta=80^\circ$ but none at $\theta=0^\circ$. The experimental spectrum at 0° is too shifted toward higher energies. This happens in general for higher values of the scattering angle θ . A search for a better agreement shows that it can be obtained at $\theta=34.5^\circ$ where it is even better than at $\theta=80^\circ$. There is not a ready explanation for this fact. It can be seen that the scaling factors multiplying the EGS5 simulations are different, that is EGS5 do not reproduce the relative magnitude of the two measurements, but it is also not sure that the original figure represents their true relative magnitude.

The right side of Fig. 7 shows total energy spectra in Cu and Au (with 20 keV electrons) and in a Cu-Au alloy (with 10 keV electrons). The agreement for the pure elements is very good at an incident angle $\alpha=0^\circ$. The paper does not mention a specific incident angle or a density for the Cu-Au alloy. The latter is needed in preparing cross section for the simulations. The formula [19]

$$D = 0.193a + 0.0896c - 5 \times 10^{-4} \exp(0.01a) ac$$

is used for the density, with $a=40$ the weight concentration of Au in percent and $c=60$ the one for Cu. A simulation with an incident angle $\alpha=0^\circ$ does not gave a satisfactory reproduction of the experiment, but one with $\alpha=30^\circ$ does. This a puzzling situation similar with the one already encountered.

C. The measurements of Darlinski

Darlinski [20] presented most of his measurements in the form of polar plots. One cannot extract absolute values from such graphs. Ali and Rogers analyzed a couple of them by arbitrarily normalizing them. Here, are presented two angular distributions extracted from the few Cartesian graphs (hence properly normalized) of Darlinski. He gave continuous curves, not points at specific angles. Of a special interest is a measurement at almost a grazing angle of incidence, $\alpha=80^\circ$.

The reproduction of the experiment achieved with EGS5 is not outstanding but fair. The simulation reproduces all the features of the data and the absolute values. At 30 keV and $\alpha=60^\circ$, the experimental angular distribution is quite flat for a large number of angles. This is a bit suspicious because at such a large angle of incidence it is expected, from previous experiments and calculations, to see a more peaked distribution.

Fig. 8. Angular distributions from Au samples. Two electron energies at two incident angles. Experimental data from [20], red line.

D. The work of Tabata

In distinction with the works analyzed above, Tabata [21] measured at MeV electron energies. Thus, it is interesting to see how EGS5 performs in a very different regime. He presents data in print, hence no need to digitize it. There are many measurements in his work; to keep the present paper at a reasonable length we discuss here only those on an Au sample.

Kirihara [11] *et al.* also analyzed this work, mostly the backscattering coefficients. They made a claim about the accuracy of an experimental procedure employed by Tabata and advocated multiplying the coefficients by a factor. This problem is not addressed here.

Tabata mentioned that the samples were semi-infinite with a thickness of at least 8.1 g/cm^2 . In simulation, the width of the Au sample was seven mm. EGS5 misses somewhat the angular distributions, especially at small θ (i.e. large backscattering angles). As a result, it also stays below the measured backscattering coefficients. Regarding the absolute values, they change by a factor of three (300%) between 3 MeV and 14 MeV. EGS5 follows quite nicely this tremendous change.

Fig. 9. Angular distributions and backscattering coefficients from a sample of Au. Experimental data from [21] in red.

IV. DISCUSSION

TABLE II: shows a couple of fragments (arranged in sections) from the history of a 124 keV electron, at normal incidence, on a 1 mm slab of Silicon. In section I, the electron at (0,0,0) is ready to move in the forward direction, characterized by $w=1$, the cosine of electron direction with the $-z$ axis, that is the portion of the z axis which goes into the sample. What is happening to the electron is characterized by the argument IARG. IARG=0 means the electron is ready to be transported.

In EGS5 all the particles, in a given history, are put on the stack. The parameter NP is the sequential number on the stack. The geometry consists of three regions (parameter IR). Region #2 is the sample itself, region #3 is where the transmitted electrons will go and region #1 is the backscattering region. An electron is counted as backscattered if it is in region #1 and its w is negative, i.e. large scattering angles higher than 90° . They are different from the experimental scattering angles defined in relation with the work of Martin *et al.* previously.

TABLE II: FRAGMENTS FROM A 124 KEV ELECTRON HISTORY

Section	IARG	NP	IR	e_{kin}	w
	0	1	2	0.12400	1.0000
I	5	1	2	0.12382	1.0000
	8	1	2	0.12382	1.0000
	22	1	2	0.10161	0.91481
	22	2	2	2.2206E-02	0.44362
II	8	2	2	2.0275E-02	0.82183
	22	2	2	1.9165E-02	0.66878
	22	3	2	1.1102E-03	0.74172
III	1	3	2	1.0011E-03	0.78954
	0	2	2	1.9165E-02	0.66878
IV	0	2	2	1.1545E-02	-0.69526
	5	2	1	1.1313E-02	-0.69526
	3	2	1	1.1313E-02	-0.69526
	0	1	2	0.10161	0.91481
V	8	1	2	9.3589E-02	0.77092
	22	1	2	9.2494E-02	0.78337
	22	2	2	1.0953E-03	-7.210E-02
VI	1	2	2	1.0011E-03	-7.210E-02
	0	1	2	9.0655E-02	0.78337
VII	0	1	2	1.0067E-03	0.63046
	5	1	2	1.0011E-03	0.63046
	1	1	2	1.0011E-03	0.63046
VIIa	0	1	2	4.7117E-02	-0.96336
	5	1	1	4.6057E-02	-0.96336
	3	1	1	4.6057E-02	-0.96336

In Sec. I it can be seen that the electron is transported (IARG=5) and loses a small fraction of its energy (e_{kin} – electron kinetic energy in MeV). At the end of the transport there is an interaction, IARG=8 i.e. Moller scattering. After that two electrons, NP=1 and NP=2, emerge from subroutine UPHI (IARG=22). UPHI just samples a new direction for each electron. The principal point is that in the course of the interaction the first electron (NP=1) loses not much of its energy and a second electron (NP=2) is generated by some process (ionization, knockout, etc.) with quite small energy. The energy is conserved; the sum of energies of the two electrons is equal with the energy of the first electron before the interaction.

In Sec. II the electron #2 undergoes the same kind of process and a new electron, #3, is born. In Sec. III this electron dies, it is discarded (IARG=1) because it has too small energy and it is below the threshold. It dies in the region IR=2, i.e. in the sample. The command is returned to the electron #2.

In Sec. IV the electron #2 is ready to be transported (IARG=0) and it is transported (IARG=5). In the transport this electron crosses to region IR=1 and it is discarded (IARG=3) because electrons in this region are not followed. It is in region #1 and has a negative w ; hence, it is counted as a backscattered electron without being really a backscattered electron. The command returns to the electron NP=1 in region IR=2.

Sec. V. The electron NP=1 still has a lot of energy (93 keV) and continues to produce a lot of other electrons NP=2 in a similar way with what was shown. Sec. VI: All the other electrons with NP>1, in this particular history, end their life in the sample as the electron NP=3 in Sec. III.

Sec VII; The original electron, NP=1, lost almost all of his energy and also ends its life in the sample (IARG=1 and IR=2), i.e. deposits all its remaining energy.

The above history illustrates a problem: the original electron is not backscattered but a backscattering is registered without being really a backscattering.

Sec. VIIa is taken from another history. Here the original electron, NP=1, reaches IR=1 with $w<0$, hence a real backscattering is registered.

The solution to the above problem is computationally simple: to register backscattering only if it is the first electron on stack, NP=1. Then only electrons like the one in Sec. VIIa will be registered as backscattered. The question is if this is physically true, if an experiment is capable to differentiate between true backscattering and pseudo (or fake) backscattering. Without possessing extensive knowledge on the experimental techniques, my guess is that an experiment measures both. There is also a deeper question. The additional electron, in this example, is produced in Moller scattering, i.e. electron-electron scattering. Quantum mechanically one cannot differentiate between the electrons after the scattering. However, in this problem there are not two electrons actually available, one is the incident electron and the other one has to be a bounded electron in the sample. To make it available for scattering energy has to be deposited, and, hence its kinetic energy will be low. As it is clear from the table, after the Moller scattering (IARG=8) and after sampling for a direction (IARG=22) the electron with NP=2 always has a lower kinetic energy compared with the NP=1 electron. On this basis one can differentiate between the electrons even if will not be always 100% correct.

Fig. 10. Differences between all NP and NP=1 calculations for 124 keV electrons in Silicon.

Fig. 10 illustrates the differences between the two kinds of calculations in the case of 124 keV electrons on Silicon. η was calculated at the energies of Martin *et al.* and presents some small differences (lower right). They are buried in the experimental error. Differences that are more visible are seen in the spectra (total energy and angle dependent energy) for $q < 0.2$. There is no experimental data for this region, not in the work of Martin *et al.* and not in Matsukawa *et al.* It seems that for energies less than 100 keV the problem is not relevant.

Not so for the MeV energies in the work of Tabata [21]:

TABLE III: THE BACKSCATTERING COEFFICIENT η (IN %) MEASURED BY TABATA, VERSUS CALCULATIONS.

E [MeV]	Exp	All NP	NP=1	Δ [%]	Exp / All NP
3.24	30.2	28.70	26.90	6.7	1.05
4.09	27.4	25.10	23.16	8.3	1.09
6.08	20.6	18.40	16.58	11.0	1.12
10.1	12.7	10.97	8.99	22.0	1.16
14.1	8.54	7.30	5.30	22.1	1.17

The differences Δ , between the *ALL NP* and *NP=1* calculations are large at these energies, reaching more than 22% at 14 MeV. The EGS5 results (*ALL NP*) are missing the experiment by roughly the same amounts. In any case, it is quite clear that the *NP=1* type of calculation cannot give a satisfactory result at these energies and that Tabata measured all the electrons, those truly backscattered and those just emitted from the sample in the backward direction. The physics at these energies is different. The source of additional electrons (i.e. those with $NP > 1$) is in bremsstrahlung. The original electron produces photons, and these, subsequently, additional electrons. As the energy increases this process is more and more dominant. Of course, all these additionally electrons can be classified as not truly backscattered.

The last column points to an increasing discrepancy with energy, between the simulation and the experiment. Kirihara [11] also reported discrepancies between the experiment and their calculations up to a factor of 1.5.

V. CONCLUSION

EGS5 is a viable option for performing simulations in a variety of electromagnetic interaction processes. This paper promotes the idea that it is a better choice over EGSnrc, from a user point of view. It is much simpler to use, the user does not have to know two languages, FORTRAN and the old and obsolete MORTRAN interpreter, and more elegant, richer in features and readable FORTRAN 2003 code can be produced.

Absolute simulations were performed, and in all cases studied, they do not differ from experiments by factors greater than 1.5. It is true that the experimental data suffer from errors, it is missing in some parts, and it is given as relative in some of papers. These drawbacks do not condone the approach of Ali and Rogers of arbitrarily normalizing both the calculations and the experiment.

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